

Supplementary Material 3. Competing interests of the authors listed as the group author ‘The People’

1. Williams, R.J.C. is employed a health company (DoubleCheq) and is an advisory board member for CIMSPA (Chartered Institute for the Management of Sport and Physical Activity). He is a senior consulting editor for the International Heart and Vascular Disease Journal.
2. April English is employed by the Cochrane Collaboration.
3. Faith Armitage is an accredited Cochrane copy editor.
4. Jen Smith is employed with the University of Galway, Ireland.
5. Holly Southall works for the Eden Office at the Leicester Diabates Centre.
6. Abi Dennington is a Patient/Public Representative on the East England Clinical Senate’s Council. She is also a retained Patient/Lay Member of the NIHR’s East Region RfPB (Research for Patient Benefit) Funding Committee.
7. Thora El-Sayed is a retired senior research nurse with the Royal College of Surgeons Ireland.
8. Amanda Doherty-Kirby is a member of the Canadian Medical Association Journal’s Patient Advisory Panel.
9. Johanna Pope is funded by the Health Research Board of Ireland [DEM-2015-1439, CFP-2012-1]; Evidence Synthesis Ireland; and the College of Medicine, Nursing and Health Sciences, University of Galway, Ireland.
10. Alexia Jeayes was supported by the Office for Life Sciences and the National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) Mental Health Translational Research Collaboration, hosted by the NIHR Oxford Health Biomedical Research Centre.
11. Declan Devane is the Director of Evidence Synthesis Ireland, which partly funds The People’s Review through a grant to Evidence Synthesis Ireland from the Health Research Board (Ireland) and the HSC R&D Office, Public Health Agency (Northern Ireland).
12. Emily Shepard is the Sign-Off Editor for Cochrane, however she has no involvement in the editorial process for this review.

All other listed authors in the group author ‘The People’ have no competing interests to declare.